

EMERGING ROLES OF BIOLOGICAL, AND MICROBIOLOGICAL TECHNIQUES AND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The development of cutting-edge tools like polymerase chain reaction (PCR), whole genome sequencing, and electron microscopy has greatly improved the efficiency of the applied zoological and basic microbiology research. The DNA microarray is a collection of tiny DNA spots organized on a solid surface; each spot represents a single target gene and is connected to the chemical matrix. Typically, endophytes penetrate the host plants by their seeds, roots, leaves, or stems. Once inside, they form colonies in various plant tissues and aid in the plant development through increased nutrient absorption, phytohormone production, and nitrogen fixation. Auxins, cytokinin, and gibberellins are phytohormones that have a unique role in altering root shape. The parasites are also known as major nematodes are polyphagous, meaning they feed on plants. They also enter several hosts at once, proliferate rapidly often producing multiple generations of year, and are easy to distribute and disperse. Theoretically, nematodes that are particular to a certain host should have developed with that host. Nematodes that infect plants have a complex history that may be better understood by looking at their zoo-geographical distribution and how they have evolved together. In addition to the short duration and high sensitivity and specificity of NAATs and MALDI-TOF MS, the almost limitless identification possibilities made possible by NGS applications allow for the possibility of a correct diagnosis in even the most clinical circumstances. Molecular methods, including the DNA sequencing, DNA microarray, ELISA and polymerase chain reaction, are thought to be more efficient alternatives.

INTRODUCTION

Because technology is advancing at such a quick pace, the discipline of zoology, and microbiology is always the evolving to accommodate the new discoveries. It focused on detection of microbes and their roles in

the environment, health, and industry, but they also advances human understanding of these topics [1]. The development of the some cutting-edge tools like polymerase chain reaction (PCR), whole genome

sequencing, and electron microscopy have greatly improved the efficiency of the basic microbiology research. Technological advancements have made previously impossible procedures feasible and have provided very potent instruments for investigations and analyses of the microorganisms. This review article will cover the most recent and significant technologies in the scientific research [1, 2].

Vitamin B complex and other naturally occurring water-soluble vitamins may be tested using the different microbiological techniques [3]. If a test sample or standard is introduced to medium that does not contain any vitamins, the growth response of bacteria that rely on those vitamins will be proportionate to concentration. The determination of the concentration in the test sample by plotting the turbidity (microbial growth) against the concentration of the vitamin using standard calibration curves. Various strains such as *Lactobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, and *Saccharomyces* are often used as organisms. The microbiological method is still preferred over colorimetric methods for foods [4], and it is more sensitive than chromatographic methods, so it is still used for the vitamins in formulations at minute concentrations.

The pharmaceutical and healthcare sectors use many zoological and microbiological approaches. One way to find out how well a preservative is in a product is to utilize the antimicrobial preservatives-effectiveness test. After adding the preservative, the test product is evaluated by seeing how well it inhibits development of certain organisms in a controlled environment [1]. For the purpose of estimating the overall quantity of live organisms in a particular raw material or finished product and for the purpose of determining the presence or absence of a specific set of diseases, the microbiological limits test is used. To ascertain if a certain pharmacopeial product is indeed sterile, sterility tests are conducted. The product's physical properties and presence or absence of bacteriostatic or fungistatic chemicals in the formulation dictate the testing process, which may be either membrane filtration or direct transfer to test medium. To find out how effective antimicrobial drugs are, such

antibiotics, microbiological testing are usually used. A significant slowing of the test organism's growth rate is indicative of this action. Because it can identify even the most minute changes in the product that chemical tests could miss, microbiological assay has solidified its position as the gold standard. Two common types of antimicrobial assays are turbidimetric and cylinder-plate. The former uses zones of inhibition on solid agar to detect activity, while the latter uses decreased turbidity [5]. Both tests depend on assessing the degree to which the test organism's growth is inhibited following exposure to the test substance.

Biological, zoological and microbial analysis

Rapid and selective amplification of DNA fragments have been made possible by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which has completely transformed the area of laboratory procedures [2]. The identification of the microbial species, the study of microbial diversity, and the detection of pathogens in clinical samples are just a few of many microbiological uses of this approach. One useful use of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in infectious illness diagnostics is detection of virulence factor genes in pathogenic bacteria. Researchers may explore the evolutionary links between various microbial species by using the PCR to amplify and sequence small subunit ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetic analysis [2].

Nevertheless, it is still possible that PCR has the intrinsic constraint of detecting non-viable organisms alongside live ones. It is difficult to interpret the results of the test when used alone for diagnosis because of the risk of contamination-related false positives and inhibitor-related false negatives in the sample. Another problem with multiplex systems is differentiating between organisms that colonies and those that cause disease. In other cases, the reported organisms in these tests may not even correspond with the patient's clinical status or the findings of the culture. Furthermore, it is possible that the observed resistance determinants originate from an organism. There would be no need to subject the patient to stronger antibiotics in such case, which might lead to the development of antimicrobial resistance [2,5].

Fig-1: Shows the various advancement features, laboratory utility in the PCR technique

A DNA microarray is a collection of tiny DNA spots organized on a solid surface; each spot represents a single target gene and is connected to a chemical matrix [6]. Microarrays may evaluate the functional gene expression and the microbiological diversity quantitatively or qualitatively using the DNA-DNA or DNA-RNA hybridization. Several generations of refinement have occurred throughout roughly 20 years that this technology has been in use. Because of its specificity, sensitivity, quantitative analysis, and high-throughput approaches, DNA microarrays may provide a detailed insight of indigenous microbial communities by hybridizing target genes with probes linked to a particular microchip. Environmental microbiology has made heavy use of two distinct DNA microarray approaches, PhyloChip and GeoChip. While the GeoChip technique can research the activity of functional bacteria by targeting functional genes, PhyloChip can analyze the variety of microbial communities. It may examine and compare microbial communities from various treatments or settings using these two microarrays combined [6,7].

Biological identification have long relied on culture-based approaches for the biological sample isolation and identification. Optimal growth conditions are maintained by incubating samples that have been inoculated into nutrient agar plates. Microbes may be visually examined and identified by studying their colony form and characteristics as they develop on these plates. Despite these limitations, culture-based approaches continue to see extensive application in microbiology labs. For microbes that are very picky or

that are impossible to culture, these techniques may not work. Furthermore, it may take many days or even weeks to get results from culture and identifying microbes [8].

By directly analyzing DNA mixes from microbial communities in the various environmental samples, metagenomics seeks to examine the genetic makeup and community organization of the microorganisms [9,10]. By achieving findings that traditional cloning and sequencing techniques have failed to accomplish, metagenomic technologies completely transformed our capacity to investigate the microbiome and their particulate. Metagenomics analysis provides valuable metabolic information for studying microbial activities, while 16S rRNA gene-based research primarily defines the composition, succession, and relative abundance of the various bacterial groupings. Acquiring a thorough understanding of microbial activity at community levels and of microorganisms that cannot be grown is beneficial. In particular, metagenomic techniques allow for a mechanistic comprehension of bioremediation processes and may provide the some suggestions for improving the bioremediation effectiveness. Metagenomic sequence data analysis, for example, may reveal the mutations unknown but critically relevant functional effector and functional genes [9,10].

Roles In Plants and Soil

In order to mitigate the detrimental impact of abiotic stressors on the plant development, microbes use biochemical and molecular processes that include

C3 and C4 plants (such as rice, wheat, maize, sugarcane, and cotton) interact with a variety of PGPR that greatly enhance their vegetative development and grain output. *Azotobacter vinelandii* and *Azotobacter chroococcum* are two species of free-living heterotrophic diazotrophs that get their energy from sugars and other reduced carbon molecules. Straw application enhances their activity in rice cultivation. In contrast to *Azotobacter*, *Clostridia* can only fix N₂ in an oxygen-free environment; they are obligate anaerobic heterotrophs. It is common practice to separate *Clostridia* from rice soils. Adding straw back to fields increases their activity and improves the soil's C to N ratio [14,15].

Because it is essential for the cellular synthesis of enzymes, proteins, chlorophyll, DNA, and RNA, nitrogen plays a significant role in plant development and feed and food production. Nodulating legumes get their nitrogen from rhizobial bacteroids, which fix atmospheric N₂ symbiotically. The present nitrogen utilisation in agriculture is 65% due to this process of biological nitrogen fixation (BNF), which will remain crucial in future sustainable crop production systems [16,17]. The primary mechanism by which BNF undergoes its important metabolic processes is the symbiotic relationship between legumes and N₂-fixing microbes, which transform atmospheric elemental nitrogen (N₂) into ammonia (NH₃). Leguminous plants host rhizobia, which include species such as *Rhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Azorhizobium*, *Allorhizobium*, and *Sinorhizobium*. These rhizobia react chemotactically to flavonoid molecules generated as signals by the host plant. Rhizobia and leguminous plants interact in a sequence of steps to generate nodules, which are locations for the symbiotic nitrogen fixation. Compatibility between hosts and microsymbionts, soil physicochemical conditions, and the presence of recognized and undiscovered bio-molecules including hormones, polysaccharides, and flavonoids are only a

few of the variables that influence nodulation on legume roots. *Rhizobium* gets stuck in a hole that forms as root hair curls. *Rhizobium* penetrates the plant and reaches the base of the root hair by a tube-like structure created when the root hair plasma membrane invaginates the cavity. As a result, the infection moves down the root's cortex to a nodule primordium, which, once released by the *Rhizobium*, grows into a nodule. In certain instances, even after inoculation with the specific rhizobial cultures, nodulation still does not occur. This is because the strains utilized in these circumstances become exopolysaccharide-deficient for unknown reasons, whether it be mutations or something else [16,17].

Regarding the roles in Animals and Fisheries

As a reflection of the microflora in the water, fishes are often infected with foodborne pathogens such as *Salmonella*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Vibrio* spp., *Clostridium botulinum*, and *Yersinia* spp. [18,19]. Not only does pollution of fish habitats have an impact on fish populations, but it also poses a threat to public health as fish and fish products may include germs that are harmful to humans. Bacterial abundance in fish and its environment may be influenced by a number of variables, including human activities, polluted water sources, and neglectful hygiene practices during the fish catch, handling, and transportation. The particular survival mechanisms of these bacteria raise the danger level of these microbes. The fact that many fish and fish products do not undergo the heat treatment method before eating contributes to the growth of germs that may have serious consequences for human health. In addition to the potential for pathogens to infiltrate the food chain via tainted fish and fish products, processing fish may cause cross-contamination of facilities, machinery, and final goods, making it easier for harmful bacteria to spread. On the other hand, GHP is a way to make sure that fish and fish products are safe by preventing contamination [18,19].

Fig-3: Shows the animals based associations with various kinds

The parasites known as major nematodes are polyphagous, meaning they feed on plants. They also enter several hosts at once, proliferate rapidly (often producing multiple generations year), and are easy to distribute and disperse [20,21]. Some parasites of above-ground plant parts (*Aphelenchoides dipsaci*, *Aphelenchoides ritzemabosi*, and *A. besseyi*) and numerous root parasites have this trait. In order to survive and spread, pathogenic nematodes that live in seeds (such as *Anguina tritici*, *Aphelenchoides arachidis*, and *Ditylenchus dipsaci*) have adapted in unique ways. Some species, such as *Rhadinaphelenchus cocophilus*, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, *Deladenus* spp., and *Fergusobia* spp., rely on insects as hosts or messengers. Host specificity is revealed exclusively by certain families of the some nematodes, e.g. The families Heteroderidae, Meloidogynidae, Pratylenchidae, and Neotylenchidae should be considered. Theoretically, nematodes that are particular to a certain host should have developed with that host. Nematodes that infect plants have a complex history that may be better understood by looking at their zoo-geographical distribution and how they have evolved together [20,21,22].

The genus and species of nematodes are traditionally determined by examining their morphological traits under a microscope by experts in the field of nematology. Morphological characteristics, such length and breadth, allow nematode specialists to classify distinct species. Previous some research characterized the morphology of four species of cyst nematodes—*Heterodera elachista*, *H. oryzoicola*, *H. oryzae*,

and *H. sacchari* by comparing their respective body lengths, tail lengths, vulval cone widths, juvenile stylet lengths, and lengths, all of which are shared by members of the Heterodera and Globodera genera. Similarly, morphological characteristics of second-stage juveniles (J2), comprising measures like J2 body length, body breadth, stylet length, and stylet knob shape, were used to identify potato cyst nematodes (*G. pallida* and *G. rostochiensis*) [19, 20,21].

Using one- or two-dimensional gel electrophoresis or serological tests, biochemical techniques differentiate isozymes and proteins. Isoenzyme typing is a subset of multilocus enzyme electrophoresis that relies on patterns of isozyme migration described by changes in molecular weight, electrical charges, and amino acid content. Initial use of isozyme phenotypes for species differentiation within the Meloidogyne family (*M. arenaria*, *M. hapla*, *M. incognita*, *M. javanica*) follows. It was discovered that the carboxylesterases/esterases were very effective enzymes for species discrimination. Furthermore, Meloidogyne species are the often identified using the malate dehydrogenase, glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase, and superoxide dismutase. The ability of nematodes to develop and adapt in response to environmental changes has been studied using this method [22,23]. In order to get results from many isozymes, this approach requires a substantial quantity of isozyme in addition to a number of chemicals (such as creatine phosphokinase and lactate dehydrogenase) and procedures (such as gel electrophoresis and staining). Molecular methods, including DNA sequencing and polymerase chain

reaction (PCR), are thought to be more efficient alternatives to this approach [2,23]. These techniques employ a single procedure for all the DNA markers.

Regarding trends in healthcare and medicine

Medical and pharmaceutical microbiology have long relied on immunological assays that identify germs via the use of antigens and antibody reactions. When it comes to immunology, the ELISA test is by far the most popular [24]. In order to get a detectable level of the target organism in ELISA assays, the overnight incubation is required. The most common way to find bacteria like *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* is via this approach. There are now fully automated ELISA systems on the market that can do a test in 45 to 2 hours (after an overnight incubation period) [24,25].

Understanding the epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 and developing variations, especially the incidence and role of asymptomatic infections, relies heavily on serological detection, which has been acknowledged for its sensitivity in convalescent patients with COVID-19 [26,27]. Assay design and intervals after symptoms began were shown to have an effect on the diagnostic performance of COVID-19 serological tests in a meta-analysis. When compared to using either the nucleocapsid (N) protein, the combination N/S protein showed superior sensitivity. The clinical diagnosis for individuals with advanced COVID-19 relied mostly on serological testing. In the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) were shown to be more sensitive than other techniques for identifying total antibodies or targeting combination N and S proteins, making them ideal for contact tracing. By measuring antibody-mediated intracellular viral decrease early on using SARS-CoV-2 real-time PCR, they were able to create a quicker live virus test that quantitatively detects neutralizing antibodies. The most precise and dependable ways to measure the neutralization activity of antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 are cell culture-based plaque reduction neutralisation tests and their variations [27,28].

Immobilised on a solid substrate like a glass slide or nitrocellulose membrane are the some effective synthetic oligonucleotides or some peptides, which are known as capture probes, in traditional microarrays. On low-density printed arrays, there may

be as few as 100 unique capture probes, whereas on high-density arrays synthesized in situ, the number of unique probes may be over 1 million. In order to improve the specificity of target identification, the probes used on high-density arrays are usually shorter (20 to 25 nt) and built with target redundancy [28,29]. Most often, whole-genome expression profiling and other genome-wide comparisons, including mutations or deletions, make use of these arrays due to the high number of probes. Probes used in low-density arrays are either chemically synthesized or generated as amplicons by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Their length ranges from 50 to 800 nucleotides. Production costs for this array type are low since PCR amplicons and liquid spotting of probes are used[2]. While amplicon probes' comparatively lengthy length makes targets more sensitive (because several polymorphisms may be tolerated during hybridisation), it also reduces specificity for the target. So, to make the test more precise, each probe is usually detected twice on the same array. The solid surface of the array is covered with synthetic oligonucleotides or amplicon probes, each of which corresponds to a specific gene. Because of their high sensitivity and cheap production costs, low-density printed arrays are a good option for diagnostic tests developed for clinical microbiology labs [29,30].

Problems to Address

The ability to conduct antibiotic susceptibility testing on isolated organisms is a crucial part of growing a pathogen in a typical microbiology lab. Despite the optimism around new genotypic approaches to resistance determinant discovery, phenotypic techniques will remain the gold standard for antimicrobial susceptibility testing due to a number of considerations [1,5]. To begin, there is a vast array of genetic factors that might contribute to the many ways via which microbes develop resistance to a given antibiotic. The present molecular diagnostic tools may not be able to handle the complexity of the underlying genetic process due to its diversity. Similarly, although genetic techniques may foretell which pathogens will be resistant to antimicrobials, they cannot ensure that a particular pathogen will be susceptible. The second issue is the high cost and potential contamination of molecular methods due to the introduction of foreign genetic elements into focused molecular experiment.

Thirdly, it is not uncommon for the resistance determinants to be present in a clinical sample's normal flora. Results from molecular approaches should be regarded with caution due to their low discriminating power in these contexts. Determining minimum inhibitory doses of an antibiotic drug against a specific isolate and preparing hospital antibiogram are two more practical circumstances where phenotypic approaches based on culture may seem necessary. These two things are very important in the current infectious illness clinical practice [4,5].

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

An important part of the targeted treatment is biological diagnosis. Laboratory equipment, analysis expenses, and procedure sensitivity and specificity are the main factors that determine the methods utilized in the lab. Still, cutting-edge procedures have firmly planted themselves in diagnostics, culture-based methods or no culture-based methods. In addition to the short duration and high sensitivity and specificity of NAATs and MALDI-TOF MS, the almost limitless identification possibilities made possible by NGS applications allow for the possibility of a correct diagnosis in even the most unusual clinical circumstances. When combined with the clinical setting, the certainty of the identified organism and treatment options promotes effective treatment. Once thought to be a thing of the future, current technologies have already come, however they still need validation and tight cooperation among doctors, microbiologists, and bioinformaticians.

The take extra precautions to ensure that no area of the equipment becomes a breeding ground for microbes. The detection of microbial growth might be a useful strategy for avoiding microbial contamination in industrial settings. Biofilm production may be better understood with regular monitoring of microbial growth. The elimination of microorganisms from solid foods is achieved using chemical decontamination processes that make use of ozone. In recent times, several thermal and nonthermal methods have been used by companies to preserve liquid meals. These methods include microwave heating, pulsed electric field technology, high-pressure processing, high-light intensity technology, Ohmic heating, ultrasonic techniques, and pulsed X-rays.

Reference

- Harvey, R. A. (2007). *Microbiology*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Zhu, H., Zhang, H., Xu, Y., Laššáková, S., Korabečná, M., & Neužil, P. (2020). PCR past, present and future. *Biotechniques*, 69(4), 317-325.
- Ball, G. F. M. (1994). Microbiological methods for the determination of the B-group vitamins. In *Water-soluble vitamin assays in human nutrition* (pp. 317-364). Boston, MA: Springer US.
- Pomastowski, P., Railean-Plugaru, V., & Buszewski, B. (2016). Microbial analysis of *Escherichia coli* ATCC, *Lactobacteria* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* using capillary electrophoresis approach. *Capillary Electrophoresis: Methods and Protocols*, 393-406.
- Hutner, S. H., Cury, A., & Baker, H. (1958). Microbiological assays. *Analytical Chemistry*, 30(4), 849-867.
- Simon, R. M. (2003). *Design and analysis of DNA microarray investigations*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Knudsen, S. (2005). *Guide to analysis of DNA microarray data*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Young, P. A. (2008). The culture based model: Constructing a model of culture. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 11(2), 107-118.
- Riesenfeld, C. S., Schloss, P. D., & Handelsman, J. (2004). Metagenomics: genomic analysis of microbial communities. *Annu. Rev. Genet.*, 38(1), 525-552.
- Sleator, R. D., Shortall, C., & Hill, C. (2008). Metagenomics. *Letters in applied microbiology*, 47(5), 361-366.
- Clark, F. E. (1949). Soil microorganisms and plant roots. *Advances in agronomy*, 1, 241-288.
- Jacoby, R., Peukert, M., Succurro, A., Koprivova, A., & Kopriva, S. (2017). The role of soil microorganisms in plant mineral nutrition—current knowledge and future directions. *Frontiers in plant science*, 8, 1617.
- Wani, Z. A., Ashraf, N., Mohiuddin, T., & Riyaz-Ul-Hassan, S. (2015). Plant-endophyte symbiosis, an ecological perspective. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*, 99, 2955-2965.

- Aroca, R. (Ed.). (2013). *Symbiotic endophytes*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Saharan, B. S., & Nehra, V. (2011). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria: a critical review. *Life Sci Med Res*, 21(1), 30.
- Nutman, P. S. (Ed.). (1976). *Symbiotic nitrogen fixation in plants (Vol. 7)*. Cambridge university press.
- Santi, C., Bogusz, D., & Franche, C. (2013). Biological nitrogen fixation in non-legume plants. *Annals of botany*, 111(5), 743-767.
- Novoslavskij, A., Terentjeva, M., Eizenberga, I., Valciņa, O., Bartkevičs, V., & Bērziņš, A. (2016). Major foodborne pathogens in fish and fish products: a review. *Annals of microbiology*, 66, 1-15.
- Afreen, M., & Bağdatlı, İ. (2021). Food-borne pathogens in seafood. *Eurasian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 5(1), 44-58.
- MALL, R. (1987). A review of the prey of predatory soil nematodes. *Pedobiologia*, 30(3), 179-206.
- Siddiqi, M. R. (1997). Techniques and methodologies for nematode disease diagnosis and nematode identification. *FAO Plant Production and Protection Paper*, 144, 21-44.
- Zafar MA, Ali F, Lodi LA et al (2020) Effect of tocopherol and selenium on the performance of buserelin for estrus induction in late season anestrous mares (*Equus Caballus*). *Agrobiol Rec* 4:8-13.
- Zijlstra, C., Donkers-Venne, D. T., & Fargette, M. (2000). Identification of *Meloidogyne incognita*, *M. javanica* and *M. arenaria* using sequence characterised amplified region (SCAR) based PCR assays. *Nematology*, 2(8), 847-853.
- Lin, A. V. (2015). Direct Elisa. *ELISA: Methods and Protocols*, 61-67.
- Hosseini, S., Vázquez-Villegas, P., Rito-Palomares, M., Martínez-Chapa, S. O., Hosseini, S., Vázquez-Villegas, P., ... & Martínez-Chapa, S. O. (2018). Advantages, disadvantages and modifications of conventional ELISA. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) from A to Z, 67-115.
- Bastos, M. L., Tavaziva, G., Abidi, S. K., Campbell, J. R., Haraoui, L. P., Johnston, J. C., ... & Khan, F. A. (2020). Diagnostic accuracy of serological tests for covid-19: systematic review and meta-analysis. *bmj*, 370.
- Peterhoff, D., Glück, V., Vogel, M., Schuster, P., Schütz, A., Neubert, P., ... & Wagner, R. (2021). A highly specific and sensitive serological assay detects SARS-CoV-2 antibody levels in COVID-19 patients that correlate with neutralization. *Infection*, 49, 75-82.
- Rashid, Z. Z., Othman, S. N., Samat, M. N. A., Ali, U. K., & Wong, K. K. (2020). Diagnostic performance of COVID-19 serology assays. *The Malaysian journal of pathology*, 42(1), 13-21.
- Israr, J., Alam, S., Siddiqui, S., Misra, S., Gupta, D., & Kumar, A. (2024). Recent Progress in Microarray and its Role in Genomics. *Advances in Genomics: Methods and Applications*, 199-212.
- Kartsev, D. D., Joaquin E, U. G., Anna, P. A., & Levkin, P. A. (2025). Droplet Microarrays for Miniaturized and High-Throughput Experiments: Progress and Prospectives. *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, 12(4), 2400905.